

OUCRU Public and Community Engagement Seed Awards Report 2015 - 2022

Photo cover by Nguyen Hoang Yen
A S'tieng mother drives her children to get vaccinated

Photo by Nguyen Hoang Yen

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PCE Seed Awards

In 2015, the Public and Community Engagement team at the Oxford University Clinical Research Unit Vietnam (OUCRU) conducted a survey of researcher's attitudes towards public and community engagement (PCE). Researchers were increasingly aware of the need to incorporate public and community engagement in their research work, but many were uncertain how or knew what PCE they could do, and often did not have 'extra' funding to allocate to it. Although there are avenues for competitive funding for engagement, many researchers were deterred by lengthy application processes, low success rates, and the large scale of the projects that appeared to be successful. In addition, many Vietnamese junior researchers are not primary investigators (PI) on studies and therefore not in a position to apply for international funding. Up to this point, much of the engagement at OUCRU sites had been led by the PCE team, although many researchers were happy to contribute.

The OUCRU PCE Seed Award scheme was developed to provide start-up grants enabling OUCRU researchers, at any point in their careers, to lead and conduct engagement. The scheme is designed to be easy to apply for and with a quick turnaround time for granting of awards. Small and pilot projects are welcomed, and innovative projects encouraged.

The Seed Award scheme is open to researchers across all the OUCRU sites (Indonesia, Vietnam - Hanoi and HCMC, and previously Nepal (until 2022)), to enable and promote researcher-led public engagement. Small grants of up to \$5,000 USD have been competitively awarded to enable engagement activities and projects that enhance biomedical research. Since 2019, the award value has been increased to \$10,000 USD to enable more ambitious projects. Calls for applications are issued twice a year and applications are reviewed by a panel, including external engagement experts. In its assessment of applications, the panel explores feasibility, quality of engagement, relevance to OUCRU research, and how it would enhance the researcher's capacity and interest to engage further.

The award scheme started in September 2015. Over seven years, there have been 60 applications and 41 successfully awarded projects to a total value of \$233,395 USD. A PCE advisory team is available to support researchers throughout the process from design of projects and preparation of an application, through to the development of monitoring, evaluation and implementation plans for successful applicants, to the final implementation, completion and reporting stages.

In 2018, the Thailand and Vietnam Wellcome Asia Africa Programme (AAPs - MORU and OUCRU) held a regional meeting for Seed Award recipients to showcase their work and join training on how to publish engagement projects and develop a theory of change.

Further training opportunities on public and community engagement topics and approaches are offered throughout the year as well as quarterly meetings with Seed Awardees to share learnings and progress, enhance the capacity of researchers doing engagement, and build networking opportunities for researchers who have the same interest in public engagement. Seed Award projects are also highlighted through the OUCRU social media and website portals.

This report is a summary of the Seed Award projects from 2015-2022 and highlights the range of approaches OUCRU researchers have taken to engage the public and communities with their research. Project leads were encouraged to evaluate the activities, and most have taken a light touch approach, appropriate for the scale of the projects – their evaluations are included in each report. In order to evaluate the Seed Award scheme, we have looked at metrics and evidence of changes in attitude towards PCE. Our conclusions and suggestions are included at the end of this report.

A mobile scientific library for children in malaria targeted chemo-elimination study communities

Dr Nguyen Thanh Thuy Nhen, Post – postdoc research fellow, Malaria Group and Ms. Trang Le, Chief financial officer, OUCRU HCMC, Vietnam

Project summary:

The OUCRU Malaria Group conducted a targeted chemo-elimination (TCE) trial to evaluate its potential to eradicate malaria in areas of suspected or proven Artemisinin resistance in Southeast Asia. The most challenging issue for this study was community participation – the protocol demanded high levels of community enrolment and high levels of study retention. The study community in Ninh Thuan province were ethnic minority peoples, living in rural, poor and under-served areas. Through this engagement project we aimed to enhance the community participation in our TME project by strengthening mutual understanding and trust. Through providing a mobile library we created opportunities for children and teenagers to access books and media to improve their basic knowledge on malaria, as well as providing a chance to discuss research activities in an informal manner.

This mobile library held a comic book about mosquitoes (“The Little Enemies”), and other science and health books for children. We also conducted drama performances at two elementary schools in Ninh Thuan province reaching about 500 children and 300 adults. Posters and video clips about malaria transmission and prevention were shown, enabling community members to discuss malaria and the trial with the researchers directly. As well as benefiting the local community and enhancing the research, this project helped the study team gain a greater understanding of and empathy with their research communities.

Awarded: \$5,000 (2015 - 2016)

Malaria Expo: fun science experiments to engage children about malaria

Dr Ungke Antonjaya, Senior researcher, OUCRU Indonesia

Project summary

The objective of this project was to engage with schoolchildren in a high malaria transmission zone in North Sumatra. Through fun activities the project team aimed to raise awareness about malaria parasites and community actions to reduce transmission. They expected that high school children would be effective at sharing knowledge with their families and wider community.

A 'Malaria Expo' was set up in a high school in the region of the OUCRU Indonesia 'IMPROV' research study. Four activities gave school children the experience of identifying malaria parasites and Anopheles mosquito larva and adults using microscopy, watching an animation film of parasite lifecycles, recognizing malaria systems and visiting mosquito breeding sites. Over 580 children (12-18yo) and teachers took part in these activities.

The 'Malaria Expo' activities were repeated during the IMPROV study dissemination meeting with health practitioners, community leaders and policy makers from Lampung province. It was also adapted for use at a malaria photo exhibition in Jakarta, making the exhibition more participatory for visiting children. Pre and post-activity questionnaires showed that the children enjoyed the activities and improved their general knowledge about malaria transmission, but did not retain the detailed scientific information. Teachers and parents were appreciative of the activities.

Awarded: \$4,885 (2015 - 2016)

Motivations and limits driving participation by healthy individuals in community-based dengue studies

Dr Lauren Carrington, Research fellow Dengue, OUCRU HCMC, Vietnam

Photo by Pearl Gan

Project summary

The OUCRU Dengue group was planning a number of community-based studies and needed to gauge the level of interest of community members to participate in such studies. The aim of this engagement project was to learn what the general public knows about dengue, its transmission in the community, and about OUCRU's research.

We collaborated with the Preventative Medicine Centre (PMC) in District 8, Ho Chi Minh City to interview 30 community members and conduct discussion groups with 2 groups of adults and 1 group of children. It helped us to learn what people knew about dengue research in HCMC, and to identify factors motivating or demotivating people in their decisions to participate in local studies involving healthy community members. We also learnt about what the public knows about dengue and its transmission in the community, and their views on the most effective means of communication with the public.

Engaging with the community in this way was a challenging but rewarding experience. This project helped us to understand how difficult it is to conduct a study in the community. With challenges from the Hospital for Tropical Diseases ethics committee, we were not able to complete the project, but we did gain enough information, and build confidence from this experience to develop a community-based study: "Active surveillance of Zika virus and other arbovirus infections in Aedes mosquitoes and humans in HCMC". This study (46DX) ran well seeing further collaboration with PMC HCM and a number of district level offices.

Awarded: \$5,000 (2015 - 2016)

Photo by Pearl Gan

Community engagement activities to reduce the risk of zoonotic infections and antimicrobial resistance in Viet Nam

Dr Nguyen Vinh Trung, senior research assistant and Tran Thi Anh Thu, PhD student Zoonosis, OUCRU HCMC, Vietnam

Project Summary

Livestock husbandry is an important component for agricultural development in Vietnam in general and in the Mekong Delta in particular. Therefore, zoonotic transmission may be more common in the community than as suggested by detection in hospitals. The objective of this project was to improve dialogue with farmers and local animal health authorities and to find effective means to communicate about zoonotic risks and appropriate antibiotic usage.

The project team set up dialogue events such as village meetings, training workshops and group discussions. Farmers and other key community members were encouraged to speak about their perceptions of zoonotic risk. Provincial animal health/agriculture policy makers and researchers were invited to train about antibiotic usage, current policy, biosafety and related health issues in animal production. These activities have helped to provide knowledge on zoonotic transmission risks and antibiotic usage, current policies and disease management in farming and improved understanding and trust among these stakeholders.

Awarded: \$4,570 (2015 - 2020)

Using debates to encourage an interest in science

Vu Tuan Trung, PhD student, Dengue, OUCRU HCMC, Vietnam

Project summary

Debate is not a common method of learning in Vietnam, nor a skill that is practiced in Vietnamese schools or higher education institutions. Therefore, the aim of this project was to introduce debates as an interactive, engaging way of learning for students. During this activity, the students were encouraged to carry out in-depth research, present their own ideas clearly, and critique the opposing viewpoints of the challenging team. More importantly, students improved their critical thinking when they approached scientific statements.

Through this project, Mr Trung conducted 2 introductory sessions, 10 debate sessions involving 50 high school students and 7 OUCRU scientists, and an OUCRU lab tour with a very exciting discussion between dedicated scientists and students. These events gave students the opportunities to think about science, do research about scientific topics and express their ideas confidently to their friends and scientists through the debate format. This project also provided OUCRU Vietnamese scientists with a platform to communicate their scientific ideas with non-scientists. In preparing information for the debate topics, the OUCRU researchers were motivated to explore their science in even greater depth.

An unexpected outcome of this small project is that it inspired the OUCRU PCE group to implement a much larger scale programme of science debates for high school students in Ho Chi Minh City. This has now become one of the regular activities of the school engagement programme involving 4 high schools, 4 universities and over 280 young people. One high school debate club, established by OUCRU, went on to win a national prize and participate in an international debate championship in Japan in 2018.

Awarded: \$1,500 (2016 - 2017)

Antimicrobial Resistance Diaries

Nistha Shrestha, Pharmacist, OUCRU Nepal
and Dr Abhilasha Karkey, Microbiologist and Vice - Director, OUCRU Nepal

Project summary

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a huge problem worldwide, but in Nepal poses a bigger threat due to rampant and unregulated prescribing and dispensing practices. In this project, we enabled enumerators to act as a gel between the pharmacist and researcher. The objective was to enable the pharmacists to be empowered to actively figure out their possible contributions to combat AMR, understand the contribution pharmacies make in the development of antimicrobial resistance, and understand the drive behind unethical dispensing choices.

We located and tracked all the pharmacies situated in the study area, carried out a questionnaire regarding the assessment of knowledge and attitude, conducted multi- stakeholder events such as 'Tea Talks', focus group discussions, and maintained a log of experiences and observatory routines by enumerators.

The information gathered in this project helped us build a better backdrop on the contribution of pharmacies in AMR and its challenges. We will conduct a high-level follow up event exploring action plans.

Awarded: \$5,000 (2016 - 2017)

Patient safety, hospital acquired infection and antibiotic resistance in the hospital – a non-scientist perspective from Vietnam

Dr Behzad Nadjm, Senior clinical researcher, OUCRU Hanoi
and Nguyen Thi Thanh Ha, Clinical Trial Unit coordinator, OUCRU Hanoi, Vietnam

Project summary

The project team implemented a participatory workshop for parents in Ban Mai Secondary School about "Patient safety, hospital acquired infection and antibiotic resistance in the hospital". More than 30 parents of young children participated to discuss the issues concerned and their opinions related to patient safety, hospital acquired infection and antibiotic resistance. At the event, leaflets concerning patient safety, and antibiotic use were provided and an open discussion was had with parents to understand their views and share with them about antibiotic use and resistance, patient safety, and hospital acquired infections. We also showed a video related to patient safety in the hospital, played games, and practiced hand hygiene by using hand rub products.

Data from the group discussion was used to inform an in-depth interview guide. We interviewed eight parents to have a deeper understanding about their opinions concerning patient safety, hospital acquired infection, and antibiotic use and resistance. We have summarized these interviews and have developed a short animation based on community feedback to share with medical students about the concerns held by patients and their relatives about hospital care.

Awarded: \$5,000 (2016 - 2020)

Link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7jXX_gttg80&t=7s

Improving quality of life of family members of ICU patients

Dr Pham Nguyen Kieu Oanh, Vice – Head Viet Anh Ward, Hospital for Tropical Diseases and Nguyen Quoc Giang, PCE coordinator, OUCRU HCMC, Vietnam

Project summary

Admission to an intensive care unit (ICU) is a stressful event for patients, staff and family members. Better understanding of stress faced by families of critically ill patients is therefore important to improve relationships and trust between medical staff and families. The objective of this project was to evaluate the level of stress of relatives of critically ill patients in the Viet Anh Ward and Adult ICU at the Hospital for Tropical Diseases in Ho Chi Minh City. Then, applying the appropriate methods to reduce stress levels and improve coping strategies of relatives through community engagement and participatory activities, disseminating scientific knowledge about communicable diseases and the care of patients with residual neurological disability.

The project team completed four focus group discussions and interviewed 23 individuals, including carers and health workers, to understand the difficulties they face with patients in the ICU. Based on these findings, the team held two health talks in an open area of the hospital on the topics of 'tetanus disease' and 'how to reduce stress'. Carers were invited to participate, with opportunities to ask questions of the speaker and the doctors. Art therapy methods were used in participatory workshops with 2 groups of relatives (17 members) to help the relatives discuss their concerns, support each other, and increase positive thinking.

Awarded: \$4,981 (2016 - 2020)

“Talking meningitis”: improving awareness of central nervous system infections in Jakarta

Mugi Nursatya, Study coordinator, OUCRU Indonesia

Project summary:

Indonesia faces a substantial burden of meningitis with significant mortality and neurological sequelae. Meningitis poses a major clinical challenge to health care workers (HCWs), as diagnosis is difficult, and outcomes are often poor. Despite the fact that many thousands die each year from meningitis, this severe disease is not generally recognized as a public health priority. This project aims to understand the experiences and perceived barriers of meningitis patients and carers in terms of illness perception, health seeking behaviour, access to health, clinical management and sequelae. Then developing engagement activities for the general public, guided by the experiences of patients/carers, to improve knowledge and awareness of meningitis and ongoing research, and improve access and linkage to care.

We conducted a sharing session about TB meningitis (TBM) with TBM patients and family members. 33 participants, members of the Pelita Ilmu foundation (an NGO which works with people with HIV), including HIV patients and social workers, joined this workshop. The main topics we discussed were the experiences of patients with TB meningitis, and how families support people living with TBM and HIV. The participants actively asked questions and shared their thoughts and experiences during the session. They reported that they would like to have more workshops like this in the future. We also produced a short film about TBM focusing on the symptoms and treatment, to be shared on social media and YouTube, in order to raise awareness of symptoms and promote early presentation to health facilities.

Awarded: \$3,355 (2016 - 2020)

Video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Lg6vXZJBhZ8>

Snakebites: community perspectives on a deadly issue

Dinesh Deokota, Director of Media for Development, Prof Buddha Basnyat, Director OUCRU Nepal, and Dr Mary Chambers, Head PCE OUCRU

Project summary

Kapilvastu and adjoining districts in the Tarai region of southern Nepal, have one of the highest reported snakebite incidences in Nepal, with women and children being most likely to be bitten and subsequently, most likely to die. The estimated national average is 40,000 people bitten by snakes every year and 'over 1000' die as a result. In our project area in Kapilvastu, one snakebite treatment center alone reported 486 cases of snakebites and 21 snakebite related deaths in the first 4.5 months of 2019. The figures, however, are not an accurate representation of the problem as most snakebite victims do not visit medical facilities, which keep records. They go to traditional healers instead, and some die before reaching any help. Thus, a large proportion of snakebite cases and snakebite deaths in Nepal remain undocumented.

Using a mix of formative research techniques - interviews with village members and key stakeholders, and participatory photography we explored the situation about snakebites in these communities. A group of 20 people participated in taking photographs and 18 people helped plan the film. We heard where villages feel the greatest risks of snakes and snakebites occur, and their stories of how bites are managed in their communities. In collaboration with community members and local health providers, we created an awareness raising film and posters and banners highlighting risks and how to manage them. We used these materials to tour surrounding villages, showing the film in schools and public places. We were able to reach a wider audience of over 800 people. Another measure of success for this pilot project was the people's appreciation and enthusiasm and their wish that such an engagement process should reach each person living with fear of snakebite. We are hoping to scale up this project in the future.

Awarded: \$5,000 (2017 - 2020)

Video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OFhehynzAkg>

Raising awareness of the impact on health and environment from plastic waste

Prof Jeremy Day, Head of Central Nervous System and HIV Infections Research Group, Tran Thi Hieu Thao, PCE coordinator, and the OUCRU HCMC, Vietnam Green Team

Photo by Nguyen Huong Yen

Project Summary

There is a growing body of evidence that plastic pollution is creating irremediable damage to our ocean ecosystems. This damage is also extending onto land and impacting human health as tiny micro particles of plastic end up in sea salt and 80% of sea fish (Clukey et al 2018; Karami et al 2017).

Vietnam is one of the key sources of plastics that end up in the ocean (Lahens et al 2018; Schmidt et al 2017). The objectives of this project were to empower a group of OUCRU researchers from different departments by involving them in a project for change to raise awareness about the impact of waste at OUCRU, and to work with a local artist to design effective media that encourages people to reduce their use of single use plastics.

A group of OUCRU researchers and artist Nguyen Minh Nam, came together to form the 'OUCRU Green Team'. The team has mapped OUCRU monthly waste burden, electricity and water usage. Using this information, the team created posters showing how much waste OUCRU creates and an action plan. The team encouraged OUCRU to buy reusable plastic cups and plates for events and successfully petitioned the OUCRU Management to use catering firms who have a no plastic policy. In May 2019, we held a 'Green Week Campaign' with daily fun activities in OUCRU public areas, displays and posters and motivational talks. Over 100 people attended events, many signing 'green pledges' to try to reduce waste. Recycling bins have been set up in the public areas. Stalls selling environmentally friendly products were set up during the week. The entertainment committee agreed to provide reusable water bottles rather than disposable water at the 2-day annual OUCRU team building.

In the future, we continue to send reminders to OUCRU staff and start work with the Hospital for Tropical Diseases and patients to improve recycling and reduce use of plastics in the hospital grounds.

Awarded: \$5,000 (2017 - 2022)

Raising awareness of vaccination for ethnic communities in 3 communes in Binh Phuoc

Van Thuy Qui Huong, PCE coordinator and Dr. Louise Thwaites, Clinical researcher EVI, OUCRU HCMC, Vietnam

Photo by Nguyen Hoang Yen

Project Summary

Our recent work at OUCRU indicates that ethnic minority rural communities are those with lowest vaccination coverage and that there are specific cultural and ethical issues surrounding acceptance and uptake of vaccinations, in addition to the practical difficulties in implementing an immunization program in remote communities. Through this project, we worked alongside local health providers and the commune health care workers to design and trial different community engagement activities to raise awareness of the role and importance of vaccination in remote communities.

Results from previous qualitative research (O5EP study) in these communities helped us design the engagement activities. These included training workshops for local healthcare workers (HCWs) about communication skills and knowledge of the EPI programme. These HCWs play an important role in influencing people's knowledge and acceptance. We designed posters promoting vaccinations using pictures (taken locally) and a few words to make them attractive and effective for local people, as literacy levels are low in these communes. The posters were put up in places that people usually frequent such as pharmacies, private clinics, grocery stores and gas stations, etc. Finally, we wrote a drama based on interviews with community members, which was performed in local communes, attracting children and their parents. We hope that these novel techniques will help increase the understanding about the importance of vaccinations.

The lessons we have learnt from this project are that local health workers and midwives are very important in influencing people in rural and ethnic minority communities. In most cases, there is a high level of trust in these workers, although there is evidence that HCWs with the same ethnicity are better received. Therefore, it is important to build capacity of locally based HCWs to communicate with people in these communities.

Awarded: \$10,000 (2017 - 2019)

Video: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=e4sP_HFpcBA

Photo by Nguyen Hoang Yen

The practice and ethics of participatory visual methods for engagement in biomedical and public health research: An online handbook and accompanying e-learning module

Dr Mary Chambers, Head of PCE OUCRU
and Dr Gill Black, Co-director Sustainable Livelihoods Foundation South Africa

Project Summary

There are currently no open access practical guidelines that consider the ethical implications of using Participatory Visual Methods (PVM) for community engagement in health and biomedical research in lower-middle and middle-income countries. The proposed online handbook will make an important contribution towards filling this specialized resource gap.

The project was co-founded by Wellcome, and supported by The Global Health Network and the OUCRU Seed Awards. Through the project the authors developed an online handbook - [The Practice and Ethics of Participatory Visual Methods for Community Engagement in Public Health and Health Science](#). The book aims to provide practical and ethical guidelines for practitioners working with participatory visual methods (PVM) to engage researchers, research participants and wider communities in biomedical and public health research.

Secondly, they created an e-learning course that provides guidelines on the practice and ethics of participatory visual methods (PVM) with emphasis on their use in low and middle-income countries for community and public engagement in health and health science. It was produced as part of the [Mesh Community Engagement Network](#) learning and training resources (www.mesh.tghn.org). The course has been developed for use by engagement practitioners who are relatively new to the field of PVM and want to learn more about what they are and how to work with them. It is most fitting for those who already have some experience in facilitating participatory processes or in using qualitative research methods. [The course](#) also aims to support health science researchers who wish to include visual methods when engaging local communities and wider publics in their work.

Reach: As of September 2021, the online course had over 9000 visits and 1871 certificates of completion issued.

This Seed Award has enabled the two authors to travel to meet and work together on this project, and to cover costs for graphic design of the handbook.

Awarded: \$2,350 (2017 - 2020)

Feasibility and acceptability of family-led rehabilitation program for patients with tetanus

Dr Lam Minh Yen, Senior study doctor and Dr Louise Thwaites, Senior clinical researcher EVI, OUCRU HCMC, Vietnam

Photo by Nguyen Hoang Yen

Project summary

Patients with tetanus form the largest group of critically ill patients at the Hospital for Tropical Diseases (HTD), staying an average of 3 weeks in the intensive care unit and often several months in hospital. They suffer from muscle loss, weakness and long-term disability related to this. Currently there are no rehabilitation facilities for these patients at HTD and high-income country models of care are expensive and unfeasible in such a setting. The principal aim of this project is to engage with non-academic stakeholders to design and implement a healthcare worker and carer partnership to deliver a rehabilitation program for patients with tetanus, evaluating the feasibility, sustainability and acceptability of this approach.

We completed participatory design of a rehabilitation program for patients with tetanus. This involved a multidisciplinary team of experts in rehabilitation and tetanus for the initial design. Printed material and a video of the exercises were designed and produced, using feedback from patients, carers and healthcare workers. These were used to support the feasibility study in which 30 patients were enrolled. Patients underwent the planned rehabilitation programme. This involved healthcare workers, the study team and carers. The number of exercises performed were recorded. Interviews with patients, carers and healthcare workers allowed for more in-depth understanding of barriers and benefits of this program.

This engagement project was presented as part of a wider ICU rehabilitation project at the Australia and New Zealand Intensive Care Meeting in Singapore in April 2019. Dr Kim Anh of the Adult Intensive Care Unit (AICU) won best poster prize for her report of this work, and this approach received a lot of interest from other medics at the conference. A poster presentation and oral presentation of the project were also given at the Asia Pacific Early Mobilization in ICU conference in Malaysia in August 2019. We have evaluated the acceptability of the program with short interviews and staff and patients are very supportive and enthusiastic about the program. Patients feel there are many benefits to the printed material and videos.

Awarded: \$9,925 (2017 - 2021)

Photo by Nguyen Hoang Yen

Regional Workshop for Seed Awardees from OUCRU and MORU

Convened by: Dr Mary Chambers, Head of PCE OUCRU
and Prof Phaik Yeong Cheah, Head of Ethics and Engagement MORU

Project summary

A regional workshop was convened in January 2019 for Seed Awardees from both OUCRU and MORU. 55 participants from 8 countries attended: Thailand, Laos, Cambodia, Myanmar, Nepal, Indonesia, Vietnam and the UK. This workshop aimed to bring researchers and engagement practitioners together to share the successes and challenges of conducting PCE, and to share ideas and approaches. The workshop combined presentations from the Seed Awardees with facilitated exercises and discussions about evaluating PCE, writing academic papers on PCE, and a 1.5 day training on developing a Theory of Change (TOC) model. Each group came away from the workshop with a workable TOC for their projects. Representatives from the Wellcome Trust and University of Oxford shared the new Wellcome Public Engagement strategy and Oxford's approach to PCE.

This funding supported 10 OUCRU researchers, some who have received Public Engagement (PE) Seed Awards. The end of workshop feedback was very positive, and most participants stated that it had raised awareness of the many ways of doing public engagement in different contexts. They also reported that they were more motivated to continue integrating PCE into their research studies.

Awarded: \$5,695 (2018 - 2019)

MORU/OUCRU Three-Minute Thesis Competition

Dr. Leigh Jones, Head of Training and Ms. Le Thi Kim Yen, Training Coordinator, OUCRU HCMC, Vietnam

Project Summary

The MORU/OUCRU Three Minute Thesis competition took place on Friday December 13th 2019 at the Caravelle Hotel in Ho Chi Minh City, to celebrate the exciting research conducted by Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) students.

Ten PhD students from OUCRU and MORU competed to effectively explain their research in three minutes, in a language appropriate to our invited audience of high school pupils from VNU-High School for the Gifted, and APU International School. A panel comprising academic staff members from OUCRU and MORU, and teachers from both schools judged the talks and awarded the top two speakers – Dr Marieka Bierhoff (SMRU, Thailand) and Dr Angela McBride (OUCRU, Vietnam) with travel prizes to attend international conferences. Invited pupils voted Dr Marieka Bierhoff for the “People’s Choice Award” as their favorite speaker. Pupils also took part in a vibrant “Science Speed Dating” activity where they asked the PhD students about their project work and career path so far.

This networking activity allowed PhD students to talk about their research with young, future scientists, to encourage the pursuit of a career in science and to foster a greater interest in science among young people. PhD students felt that the training received and chance to present in such a professional setting improved their presentation abilities. The PhD students greatly enjoyed interacting with the high school pupils at the “Speed Dating” activity and were greatly surprised by the many insightful questions and many of which they struggled to answer!

Awarded: \$5,640 (2019 - 2020)

Link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HfH0KImf8QE&feature=emb_logo

Dialogues with underserved populations at risk for Hepatitis C in HCMC

Dr. Jennifer Ilo Van Nuil, Researcher in global health ethics and Ms. My Nguyen Le Thao, social researcher assistant, OUCRU HCMC, Vietnam

Project Summary

OUCRU is currently conducting two clinical trials (33CN, 35CN) that will examine shortened treatment durations for Hepatitis C Virus (HCV) with direct acting antiviral (DAA) medication. As part of 33CN, we have conducted an ethnographic study on the care and treatment experiences for those who are enrolled in the clinical trial. These participants represent only a very small and likely very different subset of the total population who need screening, care and treatment.

Researchers have identified several “at-risk” groups for HCV including people who inject drugs (PWID), prisoners, specific birth cohorts, and those potentially exposed through unsafe health care practices (Cooke 2019).

The goal of this project was to begin a dialogue within the communities of underserved populations at risk for HCV in and around HCMC and pilot PAR (Participatory Action Research) methods with one of these communities. We achieved this goal and also continued the project in a three-year study using a community-based participatory research approach with funding from Wellcome.

In the end, two advisory groups were formed and completed a stakeholder mapping exercise. Three community-based action research groups started, including a group for people who inject drugs (PWID), a group for LGBTQ at risk of HepC, and a group at risk through financial poverty. They each conducted a cycle of action research, including how to support methadone users during COVID-19 lockdown restrictions.

One unexpected finding from the mapping meetings was that we initially did not think of one of the underserved groups that the stakeholders informed us of. This is a really good reminder that we (as outsiders, as researchers) should not assume that we know everything about the communities in which we would like to work. It also shows the great value of engaging with stakeholders prior to beginning a project.

Awarded: \$9,804 (2019-2022)

Publication link: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8863677/>

Improving the quality of informed consent in clinical trials

Ms. Nguyen Thi Hong Yen, Social Researcher, OUCRU HCMC, Vietnam

Project Summary

The project was an extension of the study 03SR in exploring the practices and perceptions of informed consent in clinical trials. In the Public Engagement (PE) component, we aimed to improve the quality of informed consent during recruitment into clinical trials by introducing different interventions to healthcare workers and patients.

Findings from 03SR suggested that informed consent is a complex issue that cannot be solved from the root within the scope of this project. Therefore, in the project, we organized several meetings with different stakeholders including Public Engagement (PE), a clinical trial team, and the Clinical Trials Unit (CTU) to discuss the most possible way to tackle the problem. After several discussions, we decided to have new versions of informed consent forms (ICF) and a support document which provides needed information about a certain disease and a clinical trial. The document is an attachment of the ICF delivered to research participants after the informed consent session. Those documents were tested with a small group of research participants and received good feedback. A recommendation for improving the quality of the informed consent process was prepared and sent to the CTU as a reference for their future use.

Awarded: \$6,285 (2019-2020)

Engaging patients and the public to improve quality of care for Hepatitis C virus infection at the Hospital for Tropical Diseases (HTD), Viet Nam

Dang Trong Thuan, Senior Research Coordinator, OUCRU HCMC, Vietnam

Project Summary

In Vietnam, an estimated 1.07 million people are infected with the Hepatitis C Virus (HCV). Most remain undiagnosed. For those aware of the diagnosis, highly effective Direct Acting Antiviral (DAA) treatment is available, but access to treatment remains limited due to prohibitive costs. The Hospital for Tropical Diseases (HTD), Ho Chi Minh City, manages over 15,000 patients with HCV, many of whom cannot afford treatment.

This project was centered on improving community knowledge of the Hepatitis C Virus (HCV), increasing testing, and enhancing recruitment to clinical trials. Utilising a multi-media approach, we aimed to target the captive audience of the HTD clinics with educational videos, radio adverts, and specially commissioned murals.

Two activities were completed for the project:

(1) Making two concise TV commercials (TVCs) about Hepatitis C infection. The Hospital for Tropical Diseases (HTD) enabled us to screen the TVCs on their four televisions in the public spaces and waiting room areas at the hospital. This occurred between 2019 and 2022.

(2) Developing the HCV information mural at the Outpatient Department (OPD) at the Hospital for Tropical Diseases (HTD). The HCV mural was created at the Out-Patients Department, where many patients spent time during their hospital visits. Approximately 2000 patients and their family members were exposed to the mural per day.

Through this project, HTD patients have a better understanding of HCV and have fewer concerns about HCV prevention. The most important impact on research is the increasing number of patients visiting our study room to ask for more information about HCV and the eligibility criteria to participate in the HCV trials.

A quick survey conducted with 30 patients about their opinions was conducted. The main points explored were:

- (1) How did they feel about this project?
- (2) Which information did they want to know more about?;
- (3) What should we improve for the future study?

The results indicated that 90% of patients advised that the information we provided was easily understood, and 85% of patients said "they would introduce our trials to their friends who would need to treat the Hep C virus". Most of them want to extend our trials so that more people can get free treatment.

Awarded: \$6,000 (2019 - 2022)

Link: <https://youtu.be/XtQmfo6O2EU>

TB Photovoices - What we want all of us to know

Dr. Panji Fortuna Hadisoemarto, Senior Researcher, OUCRU Indonesia

Project Summary

More than 7,500 residents of Bandung, a city of 2.6 million people, were identified as having tuberculosis in 2018. Our previous research demonstrated that at least half of the people with pulmonary tuberculosis did not seek care from qualified healthcare providers until after being sick for four weeks and treatment was not started until three weeks later.

Photovoice is a participatory research approach in which participants use a camera to take photos and provide meaning to the photos through a facilitated discussion. This project aims to use photovoice to raise public awareness about the community and health system barriers to timely diagnosis and treatment for tuberculosis, as well as barriers to treatment completion.

In this project, 15 former TB patients (7 had drug-resistant, 6 had drug-sensitive pulmonary, and 2 had extrapulmonary TB) and 5 healthcare workers participated. The data collection was conducted from November 2019 to January 2020. Out of 362 submitted photos, 87 photos were discussed in 6 biweekly meetings with every group, contextualized, and captioned. Discussion processes were recorded, transcribed, and analyzed using standard thematic analysis. Themes which emerged from photo discussions were barriers and problems related to treatment, including the social, demographic, economic, and psychological aspects of TB treatment, and TB-related health services, as well as facilitators to treatment success such as treatment supporting systems, positive activities, and post-recovery experiences. 81 photos and captions were published on Instagram and Facebook from November 2019 to January 2021 and shown in a public exhibition. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the public exhibition occurred virtually launching on 24th March 2021, to coincide with World TB Day. In addition, in January 2021, we also held a talk show entitled "The Role of Advocacy in Tuberculosis Control: Experience from Photovoice Project."

Awarded: \$9,236 (2019 - 2020)

Link: <https://tbphotovoice.com/>

Journalism meets Science

Ashata Dahal, PE Officer, OUCRU Nepal

Project Summary

“Journalism meets Science” is a science café that is conducted with the “fourth estate” (the journalists working in print and news media). The main aim of this event was to engage the journalists working in the reporting of science and health research and to connect them with the professionals/experts working in these fields in a more relaxed and informal environment. The event also provided interaction between the journalists and experts about their respective experiences, and stresses the importance of fact-based science communication.

We connected with journalists who report on science and health research through the Nepal Health Journalist Group or directly via social media and personal connections for their participation. An expert (academics and scientists working at OUCRU-NP or Patan Academy of Health Sciences (PAHS), the host organization of OUCRU-NP). was invited to facilitate each session.

A total of 4 sessions with 65 journalists working in print media, radio, television and online health news portal participated in the session. Topics including ethical research practice, the difference between misinformation, disinformation and false information, clinical research, and challenges faced by health reporters were discussed during the informal interactions. At the end of each session, flyers on information for the participants with key messages on research were also distributed.

Awarded: \$ 5732 (2020 - 2022)

OUCRU Indonesia Podcast Project

Livia Nathania Kurniawan, Public Engagement Officer, OUCRU Indonesia

Project Summary

The podcast and radio programs provided necessary health information from experts including doctors and researchers, and an up-close perspective from community actors to increase awareness about the health gaps in big cities versus remote areas, and to encourage positive public health behaviours. They also provided insights about the medical, clinical, or research fields to inspire the youth to pursue a career in health-related industries in Indonesia, and also information regarding Covid-19 during the pandemic period. All programs were conducted in Indonesian language and in a conversational style in order to be relevant to our target audience.

This podcast project was conducted in 2 sites: Jakarta-based for a nationwide podcast, and Sumba-based for a Sumba localized radio program. The nationwide podcast was distributed to Spotify via Anchor, a hosting platform. Meanwhile, the Sumba radio program was aired on a local radio station, namely RRI Sumba. There were 8 episodes each on Spotify and radio, making it 16 episodes in total.

The challenge in this project was to find and match the schedule of the speakers for the recording and airing sessions, especially as everyone in the health industry was busy during the Covid-19 pandemic. For the radio program, if we could not find any speakers to air live, we aired the podcast recording on the RRI Sumba radio, on topics that were still relevant in both big cities and in less urban areas like Sumba. Despite the challenge, we managed to always find one or more speakers for each episode, due to the networks of OUCRU Indonesia and our external speakers, further expanding the PCE network within the country.

Awarded: \$ 6150 (2020 - 2021)

Links:

[Podcast series](#)

[EOCRU Facebook page](#)

“What my COVID-19 tests results say?” A practical guide for Indonesian communities

Ralalia Limato, PhD student, OUCRU Indonesia

DIALOG

- Selanjutnya Dokter menjelaskan bahwa tes untuk Covid-19 ada bermacam-macam. Misalnya tes cepat atau rapid test antibody yang memeriksa kadar zat kekebalan tubuh yang disebut imunoglobulin, tes cepat antigen yang memeriksa jejak dari virus, dan tes cepat molecular dan PCR yang memeriksa komponen gen yang sangat khusus dari virus.
- Tes yang menjadi standar saat ini karena paling akurat adalah PCR. TCM juga bisa digunakan karena prinsip kerjanya mirip PCR.
- Tes cepat antigen tidak seakurat PCR dan TCM.
- Tes cepat antibodi saat ini tidak kita gunakan lagi untuk mendiagnosis.

Project Summary

This project aimed to provide the Indonesian community with reliable, accessible, and shareable information that was easy to understand about the different types of COVID-19 tests. This was provided via an educational video using a short-animated style (8 minutes) with simple Indonesian language which could be shared via social media platforms. We also included three local dialects that were most used and easy to be understood by Indonesian communities.

Two main objectives of this project were to produce a short information animated video using Bahasa Indonesia explaining the different types of COVID-19 tests, and to share a short information video about the different types of COVID-19 tests using social media platforms.

The project outputs included a short-animated video, with recorded number of video postings and views, and the results of a community survey.

The animated video was shared on 24 February 2021 on four social media platforms (YouTube, Instagram (IGTV – Instagram TV), Facebook, and Twitter). Within a month (by 31 March 2021), there were a total of 16 postings and re-postings of the video on all four-social media platforms with a total of 36,180 views. IGTV was the most favoured social media platform as it had 97.5% of total views and 68.7% of total video postings. The video also aired in a tertiary hospital outpatient waiting space where one collaborator was working.

A total of 287 people participated in the community knowledge survey, with a mean score of 2.85 of 3 indicating that the majority of people were able to distinguish the different types of COVID-19 tests. Positive comments were also documented from the comments section from respective social media platforms.

The most important lesson learnt from this project was that besides collaboration with the health experts, it is important to collaborate, and brainstorm ideas with people from the media (social media and television) to create informative, engaging, and fun health education content to attract the attention of the broader community.

The expectation is that the video can reach even more people, providing reliable information to broader Indonesian communities. The future expectation is to be able to create more videos using the same characters to discuss various health issues in a fun and informative way.

Awarded: \$ 7550 (2020 – 2021)

Link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ODsAUZV8aAc&t=75s>

Developing a Community Advisory Board (CAB) to monitor antibiotic usage on small chicken farms

Tran Thi Anh Thu, PhD, OUCRU HCMC, Vietnam

Project Summary

This project aimed to identify feasible solutions for promoting the practice of writing a farming diary. The aim of the farming diary was to improve the recording of antibiotics usage and expenditure on-farm, which in turn will improve the awareness toward responsible use of antibiotics. To do that, we established and developed capability for a Community Advisory Board (CAB) which would act as a bridge between the research group and the communities involved in our research.

The project's activities, which occurred between December 2020 and March 2021, included creating the CAB, organizing training workshops for CAB members, and encouraging monthly group meetings among CAB members to maintain public engagement and commitment.

Our partners included managers from the COCOON project from Zoonoses (OUCRU), Tien Giang Sub-department of Animal health and husbandry, Thu Dau Mot University, Thanh Nhut commune People's Committee, Farmers-Union, Women's Union, and Youth Union at commune level, and chicken smallholders in Thanh Nhut commune.

The three main results of this project include:

- Thanh Nhut commune has a Community Advisory board (CAB), who are engaging in activities to promote safe farming practices, including reducing antibiotic use on farms and therefore antibiotic residue and resistance.
- Members of the CAB were trained to increase their knowledge of antibiotic use and resistance, and motivation for reducing ABU and tracking antibiotic volume used for animals.
- A farming diary form was revised into an accessible format for promoting the practice of daily tracking farming activities, including noting the volume of antibiotics used for animals.

Awarded: \$ 4905 (2020 - 2021)

Link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=71wAck-9qQ>

Weekly infographic and short comics for improving public awareness on vaccination uptake

Phan Nguyen Quoc Khanh, study doctor, OUCRU HCMC, Vietnam

Project Summary

In Vietnam, although vaccination can provide a safe and effective solution to prevent infectious diseases, and a national vaccination program has been available since 1981, infectious diseases remain a public health burden.

This long battle requires cooperation from many disciplines, and it is vital to inform the public about what they can do to protect themselves and their loved ones. As researchers, we can help by delivering more accurate and easy-to-understand pieces of information and spreading these to as many people as possible. In the context of healthcare communication, infographics help readers process and understand complex information quickly.

The project has successfully produced a comic series about common vaccines available in Vietnam through the Expanded Immunisation Programme. The 12 colourful chapters cover scientifically based information conveyed in easy-to-digest comics which are distributed via Facebook and Instagram social media platforms.

The project has received positive and constructive feedback from its mainly high school and undergraduate student audiences about the scientific accuracy of the context which has ensured fun and engaging story development. The project team has also been invited to two conferences for young people who are interested in science: "The National Youth Science Engagement Science" and "Meet the Scientist".

Awarded: \$ 9000 (2020-2022)

Comic link: https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/12wTPvSWI3NNwRjp_tI5-xYX1hJE_lqS1

Child Diary – A Mobile App to track my child’s vaccination history and episodes of illnesses

Dr Ungke Antonjaya, Senior researcher, OUCRU Indonesia

Project Summary

Childhood vaccination coverage in Indonesia is insufficient, leading to regular outbreaks of vaccine-preventable infections, such as measles and diphtheria. The Indonesian government runs a free-of-charge vaccination program, but the compliance to this program is left to the initiative and responsibility of the parents or caregivers. There is a need to develop and implement smart and innovative tools to remind parents of the vaccine schedule, while at the same time improving vaccination literacy and awareness, as well as vaccination coverage.

This project aimed to engage with parents/caregivers to do a survey through interviews with parent and health practitioners to explore their perceived obstacles and needs, and to use these insights to design and implement a phone-based mobile application to support vaccination schedule adherence, record medical history and known medication allergies, and improve vaccination literacy and awareness. The survey aimed to identify whether such a phone based tool could fill an identified gap.

As a result, two methods were applied through the research process: a Focus Group Discussion (FGD) and an interview with parents. In total, 18 Primary Health Centers (PHC) staff participated in the FGD activities, and 204 parents participated in the interviews. Two major factors identified through this process which accounted for parents delaying the vaccination schedule were child illness and parental fear of vaccine side effects.

Parents were interested to use the proposed mobile app, when available, with the expectation that the mobile app could facilitate communication between PHC staff and the parents, as a reminder on the vaccination schedule and providing education about vaccination.

Awarded: \$2,500 (2019 -2022)

Enhancing community one health engagement for AMR

Dr. Sonia Lewycka, senior researcher, OUCRU Ha Noi, Vietnam

Project Summary

This project is to address the misuse of antibiotics and test the feasibility of education materials in improving parents' knowledge on antibiotics use and AMR in Nam Dinh Province. We held two consultations with parents of pre-school children. We selected this group because children under 5-years experience the highest burden of infectious diseases, and parents would be highly receptive to improving their understanding to provide the best care for their children. Through these initial consultations we explored current knowledge and perceptions around illness, care-seeking and the role of antibiotics, as well as any gaps in knowledge. We designed a set of posters and flashcards, which were reviewed by experts and local partners and revised accordingly. We then held health promotion events in the communities to launch the materials and gather further feedback through focus group discussions (FGD), as well as evaluating change in knowledge through pre-post surveys. We followed up the event with a further survey after 3-months to evaluate knowledge retention and behaviour change as a result of new knowledge. The final posters and flashcards have been refined further on the basis of findings and printed out for use in the communication campaign in the study.

In addition, this funding also supported the extension of the AMR Photovoice study, which worked with two groups of women and two groups of farmers to explore the use and understandings of antibiotics. Each group compiled photos and narratives that they curated as a group. They held exhibitions of their photo stories to share with the wider community and raise awareness about AMR. More than 1000 participants attended community exhibitions. We had a graffiti wall at exhibitions to gather feedback, as well as community meetings with participants and local stakeholders to discuss learnings and what could be done better in future projects to engage people around AMR. Finally, we did a virtual exhibition at the end.

With the results from pre and post survey and follow-up using Parental Perception on Antibiotics scale and FGDs, we found that parents' knowledge and attitude related to antibiotics has been improved significantly. It is clear that parents learnt basic knowledge on proper and inappropriate antibiotic use, especially on items related to cold, viral and bacterial infection. Their attitude also improved through the data on our survey related to the dose of use and the leftover antibiotics. However, knowledge and understanding about antimicrobial resistance did not improve and the content of educational materials has been reviewed to address this gap.

Awarded: \$9996 (2020 – 2022)

Virtual exhibition: <https://assets.artplacer.com/virtual-exhibitions/?i=3290>

Engaging with leprosy-endemic communities in Central Java and Papua to enhance case finding, recruitment and retention in the MetLep Trial

Marlous Grijzen, researcher, OUCRU Indonesia

Project Summary

The management of leprosy is complicated by the development of reactions, which are unpredictable episodes of exacerbated inflammation and affect up to 50% of patients with multibacillary leprosy. Reactions are the major cause of irreversible neuropathy causing deformities and disabilities leading to stigmatization and discrimination. There is an urgent need to improve treatment strategies. We therefore designed the MetLep Trial (adjunctive metformin in multibacillary leprosy) to limit the development of leprosy reactions and prevent neurological impairments.

This project aimed to enhance case findings and subject recruitment into the MetLep Trial and to increase patient and public involvement in leprosy care and research. We aimed to do this through activities which improved our understanding of the socio-health aspects of leprosy in the study areas, and to improve the literacy of leprosy and conduct of clinical trials in affected populations. The project was executed in two phases: Phase 1 including stakeholder mapping; a knowledge, awareness and practise (KAP) survey; and establishment of a community advisory board. Phase 2 included the development of a public awareness campaign for lay audiences; and participatory action research approaches to ensure sustainable benefits of the trial over time (not within current budget).

This project has assisted to prepare for the MetLep Trial. It has provided the opportunity to work with the local communities and the puskesmas in Jayapura, to get to know the local study team, to comprehend their level of experience with research and find out what is needed to run a successful trial in a remote setting such as Papua. The KAP-survey has shown us that patients affected by leprosy have difficulties adhering to MDT. Patients mentioned they wish to have more support from family members or community workers guiding and motivating them to take their pills. We have committed to enhancing local capacity by training two cadres in the community who will support the MetLep study team and perform home visits in between study visits at the clinic to check on the patients regarding their drug adherence, and to provide mental and social support.

Awarded: \$ 9978 (2020 -2022)

Developing Health Communication for Managing Fever at Home in Kupang, Timor Island, Indonesia

Dr. Trevino Aristarkus Pakasi, Senior Researcher, OUCRU Indonesia

Project Summary

The eastern part of Indonesia, including Timor Island, has a high burden of infectious diseases. OUCRU Indonesia started a fever study with the local university, Universitas Nusa Cendana, and the provincial hospital, the WZ Johannes general hospital. The study aims were to describe the clinical profile of the patients admitted to the hospital for fever in order to describe the reality in the community about how they treat fever among individuals in the family. This would be sought through the participation of family whose members have recent fever during the team's visit. With a target group of school-aged children and their mothers from one school, and adult patients in a primary care centre. One Posyandu (community-based health effort) was utilised in order to involve the community. The exploration included knowledge and attitudes towards fever and some endemic diseases (i.e. malaria, tuberculosis, HIV, and dengue fever), and how the family manages the symptoms, whether they have also their own beliefs, habits and culture in heritage from their ancestors. The result will be a community awareness program about fever.

Our first activities were to explore the problem of fever, by observing and staying in the village. Then, to target communities: patients at the Puskesmas (local community health centre), and those at the schools and churches.

Since the time of the scheduled visit was during the pandemic, we were required to quarantine for two weeks to follow the local health protocols. Then we could only reach the target community and authorities remotely via social media (Facebook) and group messages (WhatsApp). We tried to reach the community through the village team we were working with sending them links to Facebook and a questionnaire and discussing issues through the WhatsApp Group. The issue of fever, was one of the entry points to diagnose COVID-19 at that time so we changed the issue in the Facebook and WhatsApp Group discussion to highlight that fever, was one symptom of COVID-19.

The project did not work as it was initially planned due to the pandemic. The most important learning from this project was the importance of communication and learning to adapt both topic and engagement method when needed (due to the pandemic). In our situation we learned how to utilize social media for our public engagement.

Awarded: \$ 10,000 (2019 – 2022)

Fostering an understanding of clinical research through an original interactive board game

Châu Vinh, Research Assistant, OUCRU HCMC, Vietnam

Project Summary

As rich as the Vietnamese cultural history, local board games have been an essential part for family and friend relationship growth during special occasions. We sought to develop a board game with the focus on how clinical research deals with viral infection to increase understanding between clinical scientists and the public.

In order to maximize engagement from future players, game development included both clinical scientists and our targeted audience: college students of medical and scientific background. This inclusion allowed the earlier development phase to input barriers, ideas, and rationales from both parties and to integrate them into the core mechanism of the game. The game design emphasis was on simplicity, mass appeal and fun with the backbone of scientific concepts. With multiple sessions in between, game development had three main phases: core team concept brainstorm, prototype review, and balance control through invitation playthrough with external parties.

As a result, an interactive board game was created to educate the public and university students on clinical research principles and ethical considerations in research. The project was successful, with positive feedback from the 60 participants in the two pilot sessions assessing the game's impact on their increased knowledge of clinical research principles.

Awarded: \$ 5500 (2020 - 2022)

Link product: <https://bit.ly/3NgCo9P>

Engaging science book reading in Vietnamese young generations

Dang Duy Hoang Giang, research assistant, OUCRU HCMC, Vietnam

Project Summary

Engaging the community about infectious disease modelling research is particularly challenging as the work includes maths, which seems to be abstract to many people. On the contrary, the subject can be well-explained with related good stories and its application. "The Rules of Contagion: Why Things Spread - and Why They Stop" by Dr. Adam Kucharski is an outstanding book that is clear and concise about the underlying mechanism of disease dynamics in layman terms. Dr. Kucharski is a mathematician by training and now works at the London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine, and his book is published by the Wellcome Collection. Such accessible science books like Kucharski's are astonishingly unavailable in Vietnam.

The main purpose of the project was to investigate the view of the public about science and to draw public attention to popular and accessible science books, which are often missing from local Vietnamese bookshelves and libraries.

The project involved two activities: online and offline.

The online activity mainly aims to build online communities on several social media platforms.

We successfully generated three videos explaining the basic concepts of causality from "The Book of Why". We have shared these with a small group of people to evaluate and provide feedback. Once this has been received and the videos reshaped if needed, we aim to generate videos more frequently and publish these together on social media.

For the offline activities, we hosted events with similar content to those for the online activities, targeting two groups: university students and adults who have children. We aimed to give students an opportunity to extend their academic knowledge and to provide parents with resources to educate their children about science. A Facebook group has been created and two events have been hosted during the course of the project.

Participants completed a pre- and post-survey and it was clear that participants enjoyed and were satisfied with the event they participated in, and hoped there would be similar events in the future.

Awarded: \$ 2500 (2020 -2022)

Child and Adolescent Advisory Group

Lam Hong Bao Ngoc, Research Assistant, OUCRU HCMC, Vietnam

Project Summary

Children are a unique population with distinct psychosocial and physiological development, which is different from the adult population. Clinical trials in children are essential to develop age-specific, empirically verified therapies and interventions to determine and improve the best medical treatment.

In the majority of cases, children who participate in these clinical trials do so in a passive way where their voices are not always heard or acknowledged. In fact, there are very few child advisory committees associated with the operation of paediatric trials. Where they have been implemented such as the COMRU project with the Angkor Hospital for Children's Young Persons Advisory Group, not only have they provided children with a voice, but they have also led to unique and eye-opening insights. <https://mesh.tghn.org/articles/case-study-angkor-hospital-childrens-youngpersons-advisory-group/>. Therefore, we proposed to establish a children advisory board for the SURE trial (a Randomized controlled trial on shortened intensified anti-tuberculosis and anti-inflammatory therapy in children with TB meningitis) recently initiated at Pham Ngoc Thach Hospital, in order to allow for valuable insights and feedback that will help us improve the trial operations.

In this project, 8 to 12 children, consented and enrolled in the SURE trial were invited to join the Child and Adolescent Advisory Group (CAAG). Eligibility needed to be children aged from 10- 15 years, living in the surrounding area of Ho Chi Minh city, and having given assent form independently. The project involved two types of activity: firstly, data collection from the SURE study participant during their inpatient period. However, due to the Covid-19 pandemic this activity had to be postponed. Secondly, one meeting with all study participants to answer a questionnaire. This was to occur after the Covid-19 pandemic.

Insightful data was collected through this preliminary project allowing researchers to better understand the perceptions, emotions and expectations of sick children enrolled in a clinical trial. Children were happy to give researchers and clinicians feedback about their participation in the trial and the study procedures. This project has demonstrated that it is not only feasible to develop a YAG in Vietnam but it is also important to work further to improve study design and also increase clinical trial awareness locally, to contribute to educating the population, and to increase access to treatments.

Awarded: \$ 3000 (2020 - 2022)

Storybook about antibiotics for Nam Dinh province

Cai Ngoc Thien Huong, Research Coordinator, OUCRU Hanoi, Vietnam

Nhờn kháng sinh – tác dụng phụ nghiêm trọng nhất cho con bạn và cộng đồng

- Nhờn kháng sinh là hiện tượng vi khuẩn có khả năng chống lại thuốc kháng sinh làm thuốc kháng sinh mất tác dụng.
- Tình trạng nhờn kháng sinh ở Việt Nam đang ở mức đáng báo động khi đã xuất hiện của loại siêu vi khuẩn nhờn tất cả loại thuốc kháng sinh hiện có. Việt Nam được Tổ chức Y tế Thế giới (WHO) xếp vào danh sách các quốc gia có tỷ lệ nhờn thuốc kháng sinh cao nhất thế giới.

Project Summary

OUCRU Hanoi has been conducting several community-based interventions about antimicrobial resistance in Nam Dinh province, but we are challenged by the level of awareness of participants about this problem as they do not consider antimicrobial resistance (AMR) as an actual problem in their area needing to take action on.

Therefore, this project aims to design a storybook in which illness narratives are collected from patients and doctors who have treated patients infected by resistant bacteria with several consequences at both individual and local level. To ensure that the content and design is suitable with the OUCRU research context and cultural context in Nam Dinh, it will be developed carefully by OUCRU staff and advisors and reviewed by experts from Nam Dinh. The aim being to capture people's attention with real-life stories happening around them, in their community and with their acquaintances related to antimicrobial resistance: It is closer than you think!

The project successfully conducted 10 interviews with 5 doctors and 5 patients to collect their AMR stories. In addition, meetings were also held with doctors at the National Hospital for Tropical Diseases, the Nam Dinh Provincial Hospital, Y Yen, Xuan Truong and Nghia Hung District Hospitals to discuss the AMR situation in their hospitals and impressive cases of AMR they had treated or knew of. This project, however, was not fully completed as planned due to the Covid-19 pandemic and social distancing period, and due to participants not wanting to publicly share their stories about AMR. Our learnings were in relation to participant willingness to publicly raise their voice about their illness experience. We should not talk only about the community benefit but acknowledge that people have their own personal pain and fears associated with this topic. A different approach may be to support these stories to be shared by others such as their doctors or others who know of their experience who can be the storytellers in this situation instead of the patients and their families.

Awarded: \$ 5000 (2020 - 2022)

Tales of typhoid

Ashata Dahal, PE Officer, OUCRU Nepal

Project Summary

Typhoid is an important public health problem prevalent in developing countries including Nepal. OUCRU-NP, since its inception in 2003, has mainly focused its research work on it. Through various activities like science café and science theatre, the public and community engagement team at OUCRU-NP has been engaging with the public on different water-borne diseases to interact and inform the public about the diseases.

However, Information, Education and Communication (IEC) materials, specifically about typhoid for the Nepali population is sparse. From my own experience, conducting public engagement activities is difficult due to a lack of IEC material. Our project proposed the development of an animation video, "Tales of Typhoid", revolving around a Nepali character, Prem' a 6 year-old, who has symptoms of typhoid fever. With the conversation with the doctor, the video explains the modes of transmission, signs and symptoms, prevention and treatment of typhoid in a culturally appropriate setting. The 7 minutes video is in Nepali, and has English subtitles to be accessible to an international audience also. The video has been uploaded to the Oxford University Clinical Research Unit YouTube channel. "Tales of typhoid" has been used during engagement events in the community and schools, and has received positive feedback from the students, teachers and from other participants.

Awarded: \$ 8275 (2020-2022)

Film link: [Tales On Typhoid: a PCE Seed Awards Project from OUCRU Nepal - YouTube](#)

Stories from the Islands: Covid Discussion and Digital Education Sumba, Indonesia

Diana Timoria, Project Coordinator, OUCRU Indonesia

Project Summary

Stories from the Islands or Catatan Cerita dari Pulau is the dissemination of the SPEAR digital diaries stories from participants from 3 sites in Indonesia through film screening and photo exhibitions.

There were 40 participants across the sites (13 healthcare workers and 27 communities) who contributed stories to the digital diary activity. Over three months, more than a hundred photos and dozens of videos were collected about participants' experiences during the pandemic. In February 2021, we created an Instagram account to exhibit the diaries online. Unfortunately, the engagement with the public was not as significant as expected, with most of the followers from Jakarta, while Sumba's public remains unreachable. In order to reach people in Sumba, we initiated the "Cerita dari Pulau" or 'Stories from the Islands' project. This project not only disseminated the digital diaries stories and gathered feedback from the community, but also aimed to inspire people regarding the changed conditions, how people were adapting, and lessons learned from the COVID-19 pandemic.

Further to the online dissemination of the stories there was a public screening at several schools which provided opportunity for the researchers to gather feedback and reflections from the community about the stories about the impact of COVID-19 on the community and healthcare workers. An education session and community events were provided alongside the exhibition to enhance the community's knowledge about COVID-19 vaccination and to reduce rejection of vaccination within the community. These events included a Sunday mass in the church and a live talk show on the local radio.

Awarded: \$ 9000 (2020 - 2022)

Exploring opportunities for engaging patients and final-year medical students in antimicrobial stewardship programs in Viet Nam

Vu Thi Lan Huong, Post doc researcher, OUCRU Hanoi, Vietnam

Project Summary

Antimicrobial stewardship (AMS) programs have been implemented to control antimicrobial resistance (AMR) through improving the antibiotic treatment of patients. However, despite being the primary, albeit indirect and/or delayed, beneficiary of AMS, patients are often not involved in the program. There is also a lack of understanding on how to involve medical students who will become the key players in AMS.

This project aimed to understand the perceptions and willingness of these groups to engage with AMS in hospitals. This occurred through group discussions and exploring the feasibility of establishing and using a community advisory board (CAB) as a method for patient engagement to improve AMS programs.

Face-to-face meetings with target groups were planned to discuss about the media materials being developed (videos and leaflets). However, due to Government restriction measures during COVID-19 outbreaks, an online platform was used instead to support these activities.

The research team conducted 3 focus group discussions with 15 final year medical students, 4 focus group discussions with 10 patients/caregivers and 4 In-depth Interviews with 4 caregivers. We collected information about the knowledge of participant's perceptions on AMR, individual susceptibility, self-efficacy in performing the actions, and triggers to individuals to perform the actions. Feedback from the participants on these materials was used to finalize videos and leaflets with information for patients and carers about using antibiotics, antibiotic resistance and antimicrobial stewardship in hospital.

Participants showed an interest in these public engagement activities and contributed ideas to improve the materials, and how to enable them to be engaged in AMS activities. Students suggested having online training about AMS or online discussions about AMR. Patients wanted information about antibiotics and AMS activities, but they tended to have limited health literacy. Only 3 out of 14 patients/caregivers were willing to be part of a Community Advisory Board.

Awarded : \$ 4998 (2020 - 2022)

Leaflet link: <https://www.dropbox.com/s/5wpt8dswvwsoulq/Leaflet.zip?dl=0>

Film link: <https://www.dropbox.com/s/0btd2b2pacemoxo/Video.zip?dl=0>

Evaluation of the Seed Award Projects

The OUCRU Seed Award programme has inspired many OUCRU researchers to consider how to better engage with their research communities. The award scheme has attracted a wide range of researchers from senior researchers, PhD students to junior researchers (Table 1). More importantly, these awardees continue to encourage and motivate other researchers in their team to participate in the public engagement activities of their projects. From 2016-2022 the awardees involved more than 59 other researchers and collaborators to conduct their engagement projects. There has been a growth of interest in engagement from research staff, as Figure 1 presents, with the number of projects that are researcher-led now greater than those led by the PCE department.

Table 1: Number of awardees

Awardees	Numbers of awardees	Numbers of applications
Senior Researchers	15	19
PhD students	6	12
Research Assistants	7	14
Clinical Trial Coordinators	4	5
Other departments	7	10
Total	39	60

Figure 1. Number of PCE projects led by OUCRU PCE department, collaborators and researchers (cumulative totals until 2021)

Reflections of Seed Awardees

We asked each researcher to evaluate their projects. Most did this by collecting metrics of the number of people reached through the project, and by conducting end of project interviews. Some feedback is presented here:

“Qualitative evaluation shows that staff and patients are very supportive and enthusiastic about the program. Patients feel there are many benefits to this and both staff and patients feel the printed material and videos are helpful.”

Dr Louise Thwaites “Feasibility and acceptability of family-led rehabilitation program for patients with tetanus project”

“This project helped us to develop 46DX study – a community-based study: “Active surveillance of Zika virus and other arbovirus infections in Aedes mosquitoes and humans in HCMC”. We understood how difficult it is to conduct a study in the community.”

Dr. Lauren Carrington “Motivations and limits driving participation by healthy individuals in community-based dengue studies project”

“This is the first time such an initiative on snakebite vulnerability and awareness was undertaken in the area. It was much appreciated by the community that we were able to reach out to.”

Dinesh Deokota “Snakebite - community views on a deadly issue”

In order to evaluate the Seed Award scheme we asked researchers to reflect on their experience of conducting engagement. Some comments are presented here:

"PE projects have helped remind me of why we are doing research and who we are doing it for. Realizing that people are enthusiastic and interested in our work is also nice to hear. Public engagement in Vietnam has allowed me to gain a greater understanding of Vietnamese culture and people."

"I will certainly do more PE activities in the future. I think it is important to communicate with people we are working to benefit and to listen to their views and ideas"

Dr. Louise Thwaites, Senior Clinical Research Fellow

"An ultimate aim of science is to serve the public's interest. I am more aware of that truth after approaching and applying the methods of public engagement in my current research project. I will continue pursue projects in which public engagement is an important component to increase the practical values of scientific research."

Tran Thi Anh Thu, PhD student, Zoonosis group

"I am managing the Hepatitis C trials on Vietnamese people. The public engagement activities are quite new for me. I do not understand what is public engagement and how can I encourage people to be involved in the study."

"The PE Regional workshop is a good chance for me to deeply understand what I should do and which models I can apply. I am interested to do some PE activities. The PE is quite useful for my trials that provide more information to normal people and also to Hep C patients. The very first step is that I submitted and received the PE seed award with \$6,000. I am developing the 3 TVCs and one big mural at the HTD."

"I hope that it will improve knowledge, attitudes and practice of many people who come to HTD"

Dang Trong Thuan, Hep C Trials

"I had a good chance to join the 2nd PE Regional workshop in Bangkok. I had a chance to learn about other scientists projects and how they had been engaging public to their research; I also learnt how to evaluate public

engagement projects. I like the CAB model and I would like to apply it to my next project. I also want to do some projects which will help students understand more about science and research"

Duong Van Anh, CNS Senior Research Assistant

"Considering of Public Engagement of a research topic (i.e. Malaria infection) meaning I am thinking of activities to bridge the sophisticated knowledge of science to the simple and applicable action for the communities."

"Absolutely, I will consider conducting PE activities to in the future to disseminate the findings as one package to each research project. Just an example, the IMPROV study has been completed and result will be published in scientific journal. But another PE activities will also be done in November to invite health authorities involved in the project to discuss the findings. I think this is a good pattern to be done for each research project if possible. This kind of PE activities could avoid misinterpretation of the research findings"

Ungke Antonjaya, Senior researcher, EOUCRU

PE Regional workshop in Bangkok was the very first time that I had a chance to learn more about activities and projects from public engagement experts. After the workshop I could answer two questions that I have been thinking about for a long time: how we can transfer knowledge and research outcomes to the people in the community to improve their health and how to make it easier for them to understand about the health issues and its risk factors? Public engagement can also break down barriers between researchers and community, build up new perspectives for researchers to make their work more useful in the future. I would like to participate in PE activities in the future since the team is very creative by holding different events which enable me to engage with people from all walks of life from school students to those who are struggling with illnesses. Those are the good ways to bring public closer to scientific knowledge that will change their behaviors toward healthier society."

Dr. Phan Trieu Phu, TB researcher

"Public Engagement for us has always been an exercise in empathy. It is about being able to live through and being able to understand particular issues that afflict and affect communities during the engagement process. During the snakebite project, we worked with communities using creative ways of engagement to help us and help the communities themselves understand the vulnerabilities they face in terms of snakebites. Our opinion of Public Engagement has remained the same during this project - it has been a two way exchange of information which has enlightened both parties on the issue and the engagement initiative has helped us and helped the communities involved in coming up with solutions to living and dealing with snakes and snakebites."

"We would of course like to work more using public engagement methods as an approach to problem solving as this method does not impose solutions but rather elicits solutions from within the communities themselves. We love facilitating such initiatives would also be a very powerful motivation for us in working further with PE"

Dinesh Deokota, Director of Media for Development

"Vietnamese are not familiar with debates, and the use of this approach in decision-making. I applied and received the PE seed award to organize sections of scientific debates for two groups of students. After debating, several participants expressed that debates had allowed them to be more critical and less bias in their judgement. The award also opened doors for me not only to manage a project, but also to spread the ideas of scientific debates to other junior students. I hope, after my PhD, I will continue working with the OUCRU PE group to bring science closer to the public in Vietnam."

Vu Tuan Trung, PhD student, Dengue group

"I think this program is very valuable and accessible for young scientists and PhD students to develop and improve their knowledge and skills and build expertise. It is a great opportunity to develop experience in a certain field which can be a stepping stone for new initiatives and larger grants".

Researcher, OUCRU-Indonesia

"It was really great that the award was flexible and we could arrange for slightly different activities with the funds"

Senior Researcher, OUCRU-VN

The future of PCE Seed Awards...

Based on the success of the first Seed Award scheme and in line with our strategic vision to increasingly embed engagement into OUCRU research studies, we will continue this scheme in the next Core award period 2022-2027. We will formalize the support given to researchers, to help strengthen capacity for engagement by offering surgeries with each awardee to help develop an evaluation plan and support in conducting activities and reporting. We will hold a regional PCE meeting to enable researchers to showcase their projects and gather ideas for further engagement. At the end of each project we will meet each awardee to discuss how they might publish their projects, apply for funding or embed PCE in their research proposals.

Acknowledgements

Seed Award review panel:

Prof Guy Thwaites, Director of OUCRU (2016-2019)

Dr Mary Chambers, Head of Public and Community Engagement (2016- current)

Ms Van Thuy Qui Huong, Seed Award Coordinator, OUCRU HCMC (2016- current)

Ms Tran Kim Van Anh, Senior PCE Coordinator, OUCRU HCMC (2016-2019)

Ms Milly Farrell, External PCE expert (2020- current)

Ragil Dien, Public and Community Engagement Manager, OUCRU Indonesia (2021 - current)

Jaom Fisher, Research Enrichment Manager, PCE, OUCRU (2021 – current)

Dr Sabina Dongol, Senior researcher & Head of Lab Sciences of OUCRU Nepal (2020-2021)

Dr Hoang Minh Tu Van, Senior researcher, OUCRU HCMC (2020 - 2021)

Dr Abhilasha Karkey, Vice – Director of OUCRU Nepal (2016-2019)

Ms Sian Aggett, External PCE expert (2016-2019)

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